

A knowledge management system for health emergencies

LIMITING THE NEED TO REINVENT THE WHEEL
FROM ONE PUBLIC HEALTH EMERGENCY TO ANOTHER

KNOWLEDGE LOSSES AFTER RESPONSES TO PUBLIC HEALTH EVENTS

Amani was an incident manager in the Republic of Global Land. You saw her on the news. She was the senior emergency responder in the Andromeda outbreak in the Republic of Global Land.

She was so eloquent as she detailed the morbidity and mortality statistics regarding the outbreak and the emergency response measures, they had put in place to contain it. She also hinted at the possibility of the Health Minister declaring an end to the outbreak soon.

Well, that was 10 years ago.

You are now the incident manager in the small Kingdom of Scientia. Your country is going through the 3rd outbreak of Andromeda. Each subsequent outbreak has resulted in more cases and deaths. The country has lost health workers, other emergency response personnel and several citizens to Andromeda. Emergency response resources which are already overstretched, are running out.

You remember Amani. What if you could seek her advice?

After several futile attempts to reach her, you find out she retired and is living in the home for the aged. Her memory is fading, and she may not be able to give you the information you requested. Alas!

“The knowledge they [responders] gained from the response would be valuable only if made easily accessible for the country to use and support national efforts to better prepare for and respond to future Ebola outbreaks and other emergencies, and to build overall capacities for emergency management in the country before it is ‘lost’ forever”.

Health Officials at WHO-supported AAR of four Ebola virus disease outbreaks in the Democratic Republic of Congo conducted in June 2021¹

LIMITED DOCUMENTATION OF REVIEW RESPONSES

Then you remember that member states conduct After Action Reviews (AARs) of all public health events. AARs are done to identify and document best practices during a response and challenges to and lessons learned from the response to an event, and to identify actions that need to be implemented to ensure better preparation for future public health events, including actions required to establish and strengthen the necessary capabilities in the health sector and beyond. After a few enquires you find out that the Republic of Global Land conducted an After-Action Review of the Andromeda outbreak several months after the outbreak had ended. But their report has not been published on the government website nor on the WHO website. What a bore!

A colleague, who you had met at a professional event, contacts his friends in the Republic of Global Land who then trace a hard copy of the After-Action review report you wish to access. They subsequently send you scanned images of the report. You sit down to peruse the report. It has been 10 days since you first tried to reach Amani and the number of cases and deaths reported by the Republic of Global Land are on the rise. Sigh!

Although the knowledge was readily available in written form, it was difficult to find.

“... the availability of that technical information, that how-to information, was surprisingly inaccessible... A lot of the time we were scrambling around as though this stuff hadn't been done... it's not even that you can't find [knowledge], you don't even know how to look for it.”

One of the responders responsible for an aid organisation to the 2013-16 EVD outbreak in Sierra Leone.²

The 5-paged AAR report has a short background and methodology section. The bulk of the report is an assessment of response actions by

TEXT COUNTRY SIMULATION EXERCISES AND REVIEW UNIT (CER),
HEALTH SECURITY PREPAREDNESS DEPARTMENT, HEALTH EMERGENCIES PROGRAMME, WHO HQ
PHOTO CHRISTOPHER BLACK, WHO

So much of our future relies on preserving the past. Preservation is in the business of saving communities and the knowledge they embody.

select pillar. It documents what was done right and what went wrong. It also details specific actions (or inactions) that led to unfavourable emergency responses. You finish skimming through the document in 10 minutes. You then opt to reread the document in detail, with pen and paper in hand, to ensure that you did not miss any pertinent information. One-hour later, your paper is still blank. Although the report contains very useful information, you have a gut feeling that you have not found the information you seek though you still can't fathom what exactly it is. You get this sunken feeling in your stomach! Ah!

"... action reports may not cover every issue that needs to be dealt with during an emergency, as frequently unique and unanticipated events arise during each emergency. Furthermore, people may leave the organization due to attrition or retirement, and some of the informal rules that serve as the 'glue' that affords the very ability to function may be lost."

"The nature of the decisions, where they are made, who makes them, the data and information resources required to make and monitor them, and

the location of available knowledge to drive them may sometimes be unknown, unavailable, or both." Becerra-Fernandez et al.³

What if there was a way you could easily find out everything the Republic of Global Land did to contain the Andromeda outbreak 10 years ago including information that may not have been documented in the report?

A KNOWLEDGE MANAGEMENT SYSTEM TO PREVENT KNOWLEDGE LOSSES AND FACILITATE KNOWLEDGE CONTINUITY FROM ONE EMERGENCY TO ANOTHER

What is a knowledge management system?

Knowledge management systems are comprised of "initiatives, processes, strategies, and systems that sustain and enhance the storage, assessment, sharing, refinement, and creation of knowledge."

What are the types of knowledge?"

Tacit knowledge constitutes mental models, perspectives, intuitions, experiences, and know-how which may be difficult to communicate and may have not been articulated. Explicit knowledge is conveyed in formal systematic representations that are readily communicated such as books, reports, databases, libraries, or a set of rules.

Why should knowledge management systems preserve tacit knowledge?

Emergency responders usually go through a process of collating and selecting data that they analyse and structure to gain insights about public health events. Subsequently they can weigh these insights to make judgements that inform their life-saving decisions. Such a process is not always without fault which usually leads to devastating outcomes. When other emergency responders understand the rationale behind life-saving decisions made by their colleagues during past events, they do not have to 're-invent the wheel' in responding to on-going protracted public health emergencies and when preparing for future emergencies.

"It was really remarkable, we felt like we were doing this stuff for the first time, like no one in the world had ever decontaminated an ambulance"

One of the responders responsible for an aid organisation to the 2013-16 EVD outbreak in Sierra Leone.²

Tacit knowledge gained through lived experiences of emergency responders like Amani are not systematically collected and preserved to support decision making during the response to ongoing prolonged emergencies and in preparation for future emergencies.

Moreover, emergency response teams are usually comprised of members of different organizations who may be working together for the first time. These responders usually return to their organizations and countries following an emergency response as it happened during the response to the four west African Ebola outbreaks between 2016 and 2018. Furthermore, over time in-country emergency responders may leave their organizations for other institutions or due to retirement like in Amani's case or decease. Thus, those that are left behind may find it difficult to adequately prepare for future emergencies.

When should tacit knowledge be collected?

Tacit knowledge should be collected as soon as possible after an event (or during a prolonged emergency) when emergency responders' memories are still fresh and emergency response team have not dispersed using established debrief sessions. Nonetheless, ongoing knowledge capture should also be used where immediate debrief sessions are not possible or tacit knowledge is gained during routine events.

How should tacit knowledge be collected?

Tacit knowledge should be collected during routine debrief sessions which should be expanded to include a root cause analysis of what worked (or did not work), why it worked and the rationale behind decisions made.

Debrief reports should include summaries of pertinent information related to tacit knowledge used during a response in addition to the routine procedural information.

Where should tacit knowledge be preserved?

Tacit knowledge should be preserved in a shareable online repository that countries like the the small Kingdom of Scientia can access as needed to inform emergency readiness, preparedness and response. Nonetheless, the repository ought to be a living repository to accommodate for the volatile nature of knowledge.

Who should be involved in the collection and preservation of tacit knowledge?

Emergency responders who were on the frontline of a response are the main sources and users of tacit knowledge. The WHO can use its convening power to harness this untapped experien-

tial knowledge of emergency response personnel and ensure it is well-packed in an accessible format for emergency response personnel to access worldwide.

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FOR MORE INFORMATION

<https://www.who.int/emergencies/operations/simulation-exercises>

CONTACTS

Landry Ndriko Mayigane
mayiganel@who.int

- 1 World Health Organization. *Technical Report: After Action Review of the Response to the 9th, 10th, 11th and 12th Outbreaks of the Ebola Virus Disease in the Democratic Republic of the Congo, 2021.*
- 2 Moon J. *Learning the Lessons of Crisis: Mobilising Knowledge During a Global Health Emergency.* Social Science in Humanitarian Action Platform [Internet]. 2020. Available from: <https://www.socialscienceinaction.org/resources/learning-the-lessons-of-crisis-mobilising-knowledge-during-a-global-health-emergency/>.
- 3 Becerra-Fernandez I, Madey G, Prietula M, et al. *Project ENSAYO: a virtual emergency operations center for disaster management research, training and discovery.* Second International Conference on Internet Monitoring and Protection (ICIMP 2007) 2007. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/ICIMP.2007.35>.
- 4 Hajric E. *Knowledge Management System and Practices: A Theoretical and Practical Guide for Knowledge Management in Your Organization.* 2018. [https://helpjuice.com/pdfs/Knowledge_Management_A_Theoretical_And_Practical_Guide_Emil_Hajric\(PDF\).pdf?vgo_ee=evNPtBStQhwiXQhWB8Tws4UtBVR-F%2FuF%2F8jIPD4IjsJh4Kw%3D%3D%3AJZpa-qPhSrQAolcFiDvee%2FUECGRAeu8vt](https://helpjuice.com/pdfs/Knowledge_Management_A_Theoretical_And_Practical_Guide_Emil_Hajric(PDF).pdf?vgo_ee=evNPtBStQhwiXQhWB8Tws4UtBVR-F%2FuF%2F8jIPD4IjsJh4Kw%3D%3D%3AJZpa-qPhSrQAolcFiDvee%2FUECGRAeu8vt)
- 5 Mayigane, L. N., Burmen, B., Mbanya, A., Brennan, E., Vente, C., Vedrasco, L., & Chungong, S. (2024). *A Knowledge Management System for health emergencies: facilitating knowledge continuity and timely decision-making for frontline responders using experiential knowledge captured during action reviews.* *Frontiers in Public Health*, 12, 1427223.